

APPENDIX 1

An Atomic model A is defined as follows:

$$A = \langle X, Y, S, s_0, ta, \delta_{int}, \delta_{ext}, \lambda \rangle$$

Where,

X : Set of input ports.

Y : Set of output ports.

S : Set of states that the model can exist in.

s_0 : Initial state.

ta : Time advance function, Advances the time of the simulation.

δ_{int} : Internal transition function, changes the state per the time advance (Endogenous)

δ_{ext} : External transition function, changes the state of the system per external input (Exogenous)

λ : Output function, produces the output at port $y \in Y$ per the internal state.

A Coupled model C is defined as follows:

$$C = \langle X, Y, C, EIC, EOC, IC \rangle$$

Where,

X : Set of input ports.

Y : Set of output ports.

C : Set of sub-models within the coupled model.

EIC : External input coupling, defines the connections between ports in X and sub-models in C .

EOC : External output coupling, defines the connections between ports in Y and sub-models in C .

IC : Internal coupling, defines the connections between sub-models in C .

APPENDIX 2

The formal definition of Layer 1 is as such:

$$M_{L1} = \langle X, Y, S, s_0, ta, \delta_{ext}, \delta_{int}, \lambda \rangle$$

where,

- $\mathbf{X} = \{(\text{upstream_in}, \text{generic}); (\text{downstream_in}, \text{PDU}_{L1})\}$
- $\mathbf{Y} = \{(\text{downstream_out}, \text{PDU}_{L1}); (\text{upstream_out}, \text{generic})\}$
- $\mathbf{S} = \{\text{state} \in \{\text{Active}, \text{Passive}\}, \text{downstream_tx} \in \{1, 0\}, \text{upstream_tx} \in \{1, 0\}\}$
- $\delta_{int}(\mathbf{s}) \{$
 $\text{downstream_tx} = 0;$
 $\text{upstream_tx} = 0;$
 $\text{state} = \text{passive};$
 $\}$
- $\delta_{ext}(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{e}, \mathbf{x}) \{$
 $\text{if}(\text{upstream_in has data})$
 $\text{downstream_out.byte_stream} = \text{cast}(\text{upstream_in});$
 $\text{downstream_out.size} = \text{length}(\text{upstream_in});$
 $\text{downstream_tx} = 1;$
 $\text{state} = \text{active};$
 endif

```

    if(downstream_in has data)
        upstream_out = cast(downstream_in);
        upstream_tx = 1;
        state = active;
    endif
}

```

- $\lambda(s)$ {

```

    if(upstream_tx == 1)
        send(upstream_out);
    endif
    if(downstream_tx == 1)
        send(downstream_out);
    endif
}

```

The formal definition of Layer 2 is as such:

$$M_{L2} = \langle X, Y, S, s_0, ta, \delta_{ext}, \delta_{int}, \lambda \rangle$$

where,

- $X = \{(upstream_in, PDU_{L1}); (downstream_in, PDU_{L2})\}$
- $Y = \{(downstream_out, PDU_{L2}); (upstream_out, PDU_{L1})\}$
- $S = \{state \in \{Active, Passive\}, downstream_tx \in \{1, 0\}, upstream_tx \in \{1, 0\}, transaction_valid \in \{1, 0\}, transaction_complete \in \{1, 0\}, frame_num \in \mathbf{Z}^+\}$
- $\delta_{int}(s)$ {

```

    upstream_tx = 0;
    if(frame_num < upstream_in.size/32)
        downstream_out.select = false;
        downstream_out.data = chunk_pad32(upstream_in);
        downstream_out.frame_num = frame_num++;
        downstream_out.total_frames = upstream_in.size/32;
        downstream_out.cks = checksum(downstream_out);
        downstream_tx = true;
    else
        state = passive;
        downstream_tx = false;
    endif
}

```
- $\delta_{ext}(s, e, x)$ {

```

    if(upstream_in has data)
    if(upstream_in.size < 32)
        downstream_out.select = true;
        downstream_out.data = chunk_pad32(upstream_in);
        downstream_out.frame_num = upstream_in.size;
        downstream_out.total_frames = upstream_in.size;
        downstream_out.cks = checksum(downstream_out);
        downstream_tx = true;
        state = active;
    else
        frame_num = 0;
    endif
}

```

```

downstream_out.select = true;
downstream_out.data = chunk_pad32(upstream_in.byte_stream);
downstream_out.frame_num = frame_num++;
downstream_out.total_frames = upstream_in.size;
downstream_out.cks = checksum(downstream_out);
downstream_tx = true;
state = active;
endif
endif

if(downstream_in has data)
  if(downstream_in.frame_num == 0) //if first frame
    transaction_valid = 1;
  endif
  if(downstream_in.select == 1)
    if(downstream_in.cks == checksum(downstream_in))
      upstream_out.data = unpad(downstream_in);
      upstream_out.size = downstream_in.frame_num;
      upstream_tx = 1;
      state = active;
    else
      WARN("INVALID CHECKSUM");
    endif
  else
    if(downstream_in.cks == checksum(downstream_in))
      upstream_out.data.append(downstream_in.data);
      upstream_out.size += 32;
      if(downstream_in.frame_num == downstream_in.total_frames)
        upstream_tx = 1;
        state = active;
      endif
    else
      WARN("INVALID CHECKSUM");
      transaction_valid = false;
    endif
  }
}

```

- $\lambda(s)$ {


```

if(upstream_tx == 1)
  send(upstream_out);
endif
if(downstream_tx == 1)
  send(downstream_out);
endif

```

The formal definition of PHY comprises of 2 models TX and RX, and they are as such:

$$M_{\text{PHY_TX}} = \langle X, Y, S, s_0, t_a, \delta_{\text{ext}}, \delta_{\text{int}}, \lambda \rangle$$

where,

- $\mathbf{X} = \{(in, PDU_{L2})\}$
- $\mathbf{Y} = \{(out, voltage)\}$

- $\mathbf{S} = \{\text{state} \in \{\text{Active}, \text{Passive}\}\}$
- $\delta_{\text{int}}(\mathbf{s}) \{$
`state = passive;`
`}`
- $\delta_{\text{ext}}(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{e}, \mathbf{x}) \{$
`state = active;`
`}`
- $\lambda(\mathbf{s}) \{$
`MANIPULATE_PIN(out, man_encode(in));`
`}`

$M_{\text{PHY_RX}} = \langle \mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{S}, s_0, \text{ta}, \delta_{\text{ext}}, \delta_{\text{int}}, \lambda \rangle$

where,

- $\mathbf{X} = \{(\text{in}, \text{voltage})\}$
- $\mathbf{Y} = \{(\text{out}, \text{PDU}_{\text{L2}})\}$
- $\mathbf{S} = \{\text{state} \in \{\text{Active}, \text{Passive}\}\}$
- $\delta_{\text{int}}(\mathbf{s}) \{$
`state = passive;`
`}`
- $\delta_{\text{ext}}(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{e}, \mathbf{x}) \{$
`out = man_decode(in);`
`state = active;`
`}`
- $\lambda(\mathbf{s}) \{$
`sendMessage(out);`
`}`

}